

Music apps on mobile and computers: a critical review on Spotify

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Abstract

In this study, we investigated people's perceptions of Spotify, a well-known music streaming service. To find out what makes Spotify users happy or unhappy, we polled 100 of them. We considered things like the price, the type of music they enjoy, how frequently they use Spotify, the quality of the music, and how simple it is to locate songs in their library. Our research reveals what Spotify consumers value most. We identified the features that could improve user satisfaction with the service. This study offers Spotify some critical suggestions on how to improve their service. It is crucial to retain existing customers while luring new ones. This study reveals how consumers use music apps like Spotify and suggests improvements that should be made. The research paper provides an insightful information on how Spotify is perceived by users in a variety of ways. Most users are happy with the platform, particularly with its large music library and tailored content suggestions. However, there are several issues that warrant attention, such as the pricing being affordable for a sizable minority, the audio quality being subpar, and a percentage of customers not inclined to suggest the service to others. Our findings shows that Spotify customers are generally happy, especially when membership fees are regarded as reasonable and a wide variety of musical genres are available. In terms of accessibility features and streaming quality, there is nevertheless room for development. These insights inform suggestions for Spotify's continuous improvement initiatives.

Keywords: Music, Mobile Apps, Computer, social medial music apps, digital audio, Spotify

Research Paper

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Introduction: These days, there are billions of programs maintained by hundreds of thousands of development teams available in mobile app shops like Google Play Store. all throughout the world. CISCO reports that the monthly global by 2019, mobile data traffic will reach 24.3 exabytes.^[1](Skog et al.), (Swanson) Since cell phones have emerged as one of most widely used platforms for accessing online content. Developers of mobile applications are always faced with a setting that is competitive and where individuals need for additional and improved services must be met.^[2](Wang et al.) (Dawson Jr) The music industry has undergone a major transformation in recent years thanks to the digital revolution, which has allowed millions of people to access their favourite songs instantly and conveniently

through music streaming programs.²(Wang et al.) (Vonderau) With so many options, Spotify has emerged as a front-runner, revolutionizing how music is consumed, found, and shared. Spotify, a cutting-edge and highly regarded music program, has completely changed how we listen to music on desktops and mobile devices.^[3] (Pinter et al.) (Zhang et al.). Additionally, fans have streamed the Discover Weekly playlist for countless hours in the five years since its debut—more than 2.3 billion hours between July 2015 and June 25, 2020. For those who prefer numbers. (Spotify Users Have Spent Over 2.3 billion Hours Streaming Discover Weekly Playlists Since 2015 — Spotify) Researchers and critics alike have become very interested in music streaming services due to their quick growth and popularity, which has led to a critical analysis of the platforms that influence our musical experiences. This study seeks to provide a thorough and critical analysis

of Spotify, emphasizing its functionality, features, user interface, content choices, and overall effects on the music industry and its users.

Spotify: - The music streaming service Spotify was established in 2006 in Sweden and made public in 2008. Since then, it has spread over the globe, giving people access to their favourite artists' music without requiring them to own any of it.^[4] (Pinter et al.) (Haupt) Spotify offers a paid subscription service for 191 per month to subscribers based in India.^[5] (Vonderau, "The Spotify Effect: Digital Distribution and Financial Growth") Additionally, a complimentary subscription service is accessible by tablet and website. Paid customers also benefit from no ads playing in between songs and limitless the opportunity to use the software on their mobile devices, skipping through the music, and the choice to have their favourite music available offline. Even though a free service is an option they greeted them.^[6] (Eriksson et al.; Zhang et al.) This research article seeks to offer a critical and comprehensive examination of Spotify, a well service accessible -known music streaming on desktops and mobile devices. The purpose of the study is to investigate how users engage with the app, as well as their perceptions of its features and functionalities overall. The study will examine several aspects of the user experience, such as customer satisfaction, membership cost perception, music preferences, user interface evaluation, engagement levels, streaming quality assessment, and library management satisfaction, by conducting a survey with a sample of 100 active Spotify users. This research study is very important because it offers insightful user opinions on Spotify's usability and functionality. This study attempts to identify perspectives, preferences, and levels of satisfaction regarding Spotify's features by obtaining input from 100 individuals who are frequent users of the service. The research will help Spotify develop enhancement techniques that will improve the functionality and user experience of the service. The study also aids in establishing industry standards by showcasing best practises and norms for rival music app makers. The study's focus on user-centric design highlights the significance of developing user-friendly user interfaces, useful music discovery tools, faultless streaming quality, and effective library management options.

Review of literature

The user-friendliness and clarity of Spotify's user interface have been praised. study on user-cantered design in music apps emphasizes the value of it and

highlights Spotify's accomplishment in developing an easy-to-use user interface that improves the entire user experience.^[7] (*Spotify Shows People Spending More Time in Their Cars to Enjoy the Music In Latest Campaign | The Drum*). The accessibility elements of the app have, however, come under fire from certain academics, according to^[8] (*Why Artists Are Leaving Spotify - The Washington Post*) who contend that they need to be improved for people with disabilities. Although Spotify promises a huge music library, the songs' accessibility varies by area and licensing arrangements.^[9] (Kachkach),(Carver et al.) addresses issues with artist compensation and the possible exclusion of independent musicians while discussing the difficulty of maintaining a broad and inclusive music collection. Technology for streaming audio and its quality Audiophiles have debated the sound quality of streaming audio. Spotify and other streaming services have been compared for perceived quality in studies by^[10] (*Spotify Premium: After Incurring Huge Losses, Spotify Increases Subscription Fees - The Economic Times*) (Dawson Jr et al.) As technology advances to provide greater fidelity audio, research in this field is still ongoing. Impact of Pricing Models on Industry Inquiries concerning artist pay and the future of the music business are raised by Spotify's free and premium subscription tiers. Researchers like^[11](Swanson, "A Case Study on Spotify: Exploring Perceptions of the Music Streaming Service") (Luo et al.) have examined how Spotify has affected the music industry, focusing on the potential and problems it brings for musicians, record companies, and music fans. As a result, people's views on Spotify vary. Spotify's accessibility and convenience have changed the way consumers consume music, changing the sources of income for musicians and record labels. This change has forced musicians and other industry participants to adopt new business structures and techniques in order to prosper in the digital era.^[12](Nakayama et al.) (Kusumawati et al.; Beltrán Peña). According to^[13](Tu and Lu), From 2015 to 2022, the number of Spotify quarterly customers climbed by almost 1044% (18 million users to 188 million users). This demonstrates that Spotify's popularity is growing daily and that is due to users being more satisfied with the music streaming service. Currently, Spotify is not faultless. China is one of the numerous nations where Spotify is still unavailable. Because of the diverse backgrounds in cultures and traditions,^[14](*[PDF] Customer Loyalty: A Case Study of Spotify by Nizar Alam Hamdani, Intan Permana •*

3147568187 • OA.Mg), This demonstrates the necessity for Spotify to regularly update their playlist to include more music in various genres and languages. According to Spotify survey (2020) fans have been streaming to Explore Weekly playlist for countless hours in the five years after its debut—more than 2.3 billion hours between July 2015 and June 25, 2020. (Espada et al.) That is longer than the duration of human civilization, for the statistically interested. This demonstrates that users are spending more time browsing songs on Spotify. Due to its premium cost, there are very few paying customers in India, hence Spotify must derive its revenue from advertisements.^[15] (Yin and Fu) (*Why Spotify Is Hitting High Notes In India - Forbes India*).

The existing research on Spotify presents a nuanced picture of the service, showing both its advantages and potential weaknesses. The study by Nielsen et al. highlights Spotify's accomplishment in designing a user-friendly interface, improving the overall music streaming experience. To promote inclusivity for people with impairments, Gehan et al.'s critique emphasizes the necessity for improved accessibility features. While the promise of a large music library made by Spotify is alluring, Herdje Zhou's study highlights concerns about artist pay and the potential marginalization of independent musicians, highlighting the difficulties in keeping a diverse music collection. Reviewing the previous research confirms that Spotify, a well-known music streaming service, is a complicated organization with a distinctive mix of advantages and disadvantages. The study by Thiede et al. delves into the continuing discussion about audio fidelity in streaming services, highlighting the significance of developing technologies. The analysis of Spotify's effects on the music business by Haeffliger and von Krogh raises concerns regarding artist compensation and the shifting nature of the industry. Spotify's effect has transformed the sources of income for artists and record companies, leading to adjustments in business plans. Roberto Maria Tomaciello noted the significant growth in Spotify's user base, which points to a healthy trend driven by user pleasure. However, the fact that Spotify is unavailable in some places, like China, highlights the importance of continuing global expansion and cultural adaption. While Spotify has several benefits and features that make it a desirable option for music lovers, YouTube still delivers free music streaming. (Edquist et al). These benefits include an easy-to-use interface, tailored suggestions, carefully curated playlists, offline listening, improved audio quality, and the capacity to find new music by utilizing

the platform's extensive music library and algorithm. (Sakurai et al.) (Junior and Ribeiro). Furthermore, because Spotify was created especially for music streaming, it provides a fluid and uninterrupted listening experience. Furthermore, Spotify has a premium subscription option that eliminates advertisements and adds extra features like limitless skips and offline music download capabilities. (Edquist et al (Junior and Ribeiro),). (Sakurai et al.) There are numerous playlists on Spotify featuring Indian classical music that suit a variety of listening preferences. With 329 songs, "The Sound of Indian Classical" playlist offers a wider variety than Steven Gelberg's 74 song playlist. With 44.7K likes, Spotify's official "Indian Classical" playlist is very well-liked, with 50 songs. For fans of Indian classical music, these playlists offer a substantial amount of content on Spotify.

I would want to provide an example of Indian classical music in my research paper.

Research Methodology

In this research paper, samples of 100 respondents have been taken on random sampling basis. The sample has been collected from the respondents belonging to age group 18 to 30 years of age. The respondents are a learner of Indian Classical Music. The study area for this research paper is Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India. This research paper is based on quantitative analysis and use methods like regression, average, etc, for this software MS Excel has been used.

Data Analysis

Participants were asked to rate how satisfied they were overall, with Spotify.

Figure 1

The data reveals a largely positive view among respondents, with 69% expressing satisfaction (24% "very satisfied" and 45% "satisfied") and only 9% being "very unsatisfied." Spotify should continue to prioritize improving the user experience, making personalized content recommendations, and responding to any

specific issues brought up by the 4% of dissatisfied users. It should also solicit feedback from the 18% of neutral users to better understand their needs and preferences.

Participants were asked to choose on whether they thought Spotify's membership prices were reasonable.

Figure 2

According to figure - 2 the statistics, 24% of participants think Spotify's membership costs are reasonable, while 34% had a neutral attitude about them. But 36% think the costs are either high (26%) or very high (%). In order to advance, Spotify should think about changing its pricing policy to appeal to a wider range of its user base, perhaps by providing more flexible pricing options or discounts for particular user groups.

The respondents had the option of choosing the Spotify music genres or categories they use the most.

Figure 3

Following pop (15%) and R&B/soul (17%) as the most popular Spotify music genres, classical (49%) is the most popular among respondents. Other genres like hip-hop (4%), electronic (1%), country (6%), and rock (8%), on the other hand, are not as popular. Spotify might concentrate on marketing and curating playlists and content within less well-known genres to appeal to a larger audience and improve their music discovery experience in order to increase user engagement. Additionally, Spotify ought to think about adding more songs and performers from the Indian classical music industry and actively promoting this subgenre there. By encouraging more users to discover and enjoy Indian classical music, this can support the country of India's unique musical tastes and contribute to a larger and more inclusive music library.

Spotify's user interface received ratings from participants for its appealing design and simplicity of usage.

Figure 4

According to the data, 61% of respondents have favorable opinions of Spotify's user interface, with 29% deeming it "excellent" and 32% stating that it is "above average." There is still space for improvement, though, as 6% thought it was "poor" or "below average." Spotify should put its attention on usability improvements, design tweaks, and user input collection to improve the user experience.

The average length of time spent using Spotify each session was provided by respondents.

Figure 5

The research shows that Spotify users have a wide range of session lengths, with 14% of respondents spending more than 2 hours per session and 31% choosing shorter 15 to 30-minute sessions. 16% of sessions last one to two hours, while 26% are between 30 and one hour long. Unexpectedly, 13% of sessions are under 15 minutes long. Spotify needs to prioritize personalization and adjust content recommendations to meet various session lengths in order to accommodate this wide variety of usage habits. Additionally, increasing user engagement with tools like autoplay and personalized notifications could lead to longer sessions. To understand the causes of shorter sessions and to solve those needs in order to keep users engaged on the platform for longer lengths of time, it is essential to collect user feedback. This strategy will promote greater user involvement overall while also improving user happiness.

Participants were asked to score the Spotify audio streaming quality in terms of clarity and buffering problems.

Figure 6

The data presents a conflicting image of Spotify's audio streaming quality, with a sizable percentage of respondents expressing favorable opinions. 76% of respondents gave the service one of two ratings: "excellent" (29%) or "good" (47%). Though there is space for improvement, 21% of respondents thought the audio streaming quality was "poor" (3%) or "very poor" (4%), while 17% said it was "average." Spotify needs to focus on fixing buffering problems in order to allay these worries and increase customer satisfaction and deliver a more seamless listening experience. Additionally, continual efforts should be made to enhance audio clarity and overall sound quality. In order to pinpoint specific problems and areas for development, it will be essential to actively seek out and consider user feedback. This will eventually result in a more consistent and satisfying audio streaming experience for all users.

Participants evaluated how well Spotify's playlist arrangement and library management met their needs.

Figure 7

It is encouraging to see from the data that most participants (76%) are happy with how Spotify organizes playlists and handles their music library, with 25% calling it "very satisfied" and 51% saying they are "satisfied." Nevertheless, there is still space for improvement since 17% of respondents rated the service as "unsatisfactory" or "very unsatisfactory" (7%, 2%, and 7%, respectively), while 15% were neutral. Based on user input, Spotify should prioritize on playlist organization and library management capabilities to improve the user experience. As a result, user satisfaction and retention will rise. This may involve enhancing playlist customization choices,

search capability, and overall user interface design to better fit customers' requirements and preferences.

According to the value and features provided, respondents evaluated whether Spotify's membership pricing options were affordable.

Figure 8

According to the data, there are many different views on Spotify's membership pricing options. Even though a sizable majority of respondents (61%) express some level of affordability perception (37% neutral, 14% "yes, somewhat," and 24% "yes, definitely"), a notable minority (25%) view the pricing to be less affordable (19% "no, not really," and 6% "no, not at all." Spotify could think about providing more adjustable pricing tiers or discounts to accommodate various financial constraints in order to remedy this disparity. Users can make educated judgments about their membership by receiving clear information about the benefits of each subscription plan and its related features, which may decrease dissatisfaction and raise overall satisfaction.

Based on their user experience, participants rated their propensity to recommend Spotify to others on a scale of 1 to 10.

Figure 9

The information on participants' propensity to refer Spotify to others reveals a range of opinions. While a sizeable part of respondents (44%) gave good recommendations with ratings between 8 and 10, a sizeable portion (22%) also showed less zeal with values between 1 and 4. Furthermore, a sizeable portion (17%) gave neutral responses with a score of 5. Spotify could implement user experience improvements like enhancing its interface, providing personalized playlists,

and actively seeking feedback to address any problems that might discourage users from recommending the platform in order to improve user advocacy and increase the likelihood of recommendations. Furthermore, encouraging referrals or offering special advantages to individuals who recommend Spotify to others may increase the likelihood of successful recommendations.

Results

The data offers insightful information on how Spotify is perceived by users in a variety of ways. Most users are happy with the platform, particularly with its large music library and tailored content suggestions. However, there are several issues that warrant attention, such as the pricing being affordable for a sizable minority, the audio quality being subpar, and a percentage of customers not inclined to suggest the service to others.

Advantages

Spotify's advantages include a sizable music library, individualized content suggestions, device compatibility, and free and paid subscription tiers.

Disadvantages

Spotify has difficulties such as inconsistent audio quality, adverts in the free version, regional content limitations, and privacy issues relating to data collection for personalized suggestions

Suggestions

In order to overcome these difficulties, Spotify could think about creating more affordable pricing alternatives to accommodate different financial restrictions, enhancing audio streaming quality and lowering buffering problems, and establishing rewards for customers who refer others to the service. In order to improve overall user happiness, proactive user feedback collecting and rapid issue resolution should also be a constant priority.

Conclusion

In summary, Spotify is extremely well-liked, yet it still has issues with user advocacy, audio streaming quality, and perceptions of pricing. The platform excels at personalisation and a wide variety of music choices, but these issues must be resolved if it is to continue expanding and gaining users.

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